

Feasibility Analysis of Laying Chicken Breeder Businesses in Marketing, Financial and Environmental Aspects

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ABSTRACT

This type of research is qualitative research. The method used in this research is a combination of qualitative methods on marketing and environmental aspects and then quantitative methods on financial aspects. The qualitative research method is an interview process regarding the understanding of a matter to obtain data, information, texts of the views of respondents using various methodologies on a problem. The quantitative method is data retrieval based on the numerical calculation data collected and then added up. This study aims to obtain data and information as well as responses when the research is taking place with what is in the field. This writing method uses a centralized interview method by obtaining information by means of face-to-face or online question and answer between the researcher (as an interviewer with or without using an interview guide) and the subject under study and using observation or direct observation by looking at the cage situation, marketing and his finances. The results of the study show that (1) based on the marketing aspect, looking at the market, demand conditions are stable and continue to increase every year due to the egg sales strategy so that this business is feasible to run for 3 years. (2) based on the financial aspect, it can be seen that from 2020-2023 it has increased even though the number of chickens has decreased because the cost of buying seeds was not calculated in 2021, while in 2023 there was an addition of seeds so that it can be seen that profits have increased from 2020-2021. (3) based on environmental aspects it is very conducive, it is kept clean and healthy, so there are no problems in the environment because it has been anticipated by the farm so it is feasible to run. The conclusion of the study shows that marketing, financial and environmental aspects in the feasibility analysis of a small-scale laying hen business are feasible to run because they have fulfilled all the aspects carried out.

INTRODUCTION

Animal husbandry is the activity of keeping livestock for cultivation and gaining profits from this activity. The definition of breeder is not limited to maintenance alone, the difference between raising and animal husbandry lies in the objectives.

Our business in laying hens is aimed at selling eggs from our own rearing in small-scale cages for 3 years, namely in 2020 around 50 laying hens, in 2021 around 40 laying hens and in 2022 an increase of around 335 laying hens with a cage area of 4m². And we will also show the initial capital from purchasing chicken seeds (DOC) until the chicken is ready to lay eggs (17 weeks).

This laying hen business really requires a lot of capital and it is also recommended that before starting it, it would be good to learn from experts such as experienced breeders so that when you do it, the risks involved are not too big.

In a business and in the laying hen business there will definitely be failures even though you have studied and understood it, but the process of failure in a business will result in real experiences that will be experienced or learning that is delayed so keep analyzing, learning and also don't give up.

When planning a laying hen farming business, you can do it by analyzing its feasibility first so that when you want to run the business you will easily know the bad and good sides of managing it.

Small-scale laying hen farming is the rearing of brown breed chickens including housing, feed and health management, selection, rejuvenation, beak trimming, and others. In Law No. 18 of 2009, business in the livestock sector is an activity that produces products and services that support the livestock cultivation business.

Eggs are the main source of protein and are also cheap for Indonesian people. Currently, domestic demand for eggs continues to increase in line with the increase in human birth rates, increasing the need for animal protein derived from eggs. The increasing need for eggs must be balanced with large egg production so that there is no shortage of egg supplies which can result in expensive egg prices.

Eggs are also a daily staple food that is in great demand and very few people want to breed them because of constraints on capital and space, so by analyzing this as a farmer you can find out a little about whether the business is worth running or not. Along with the development of the laying hen era, there is factory-processed feed which is processed with advanced technology and is also very complete with lots of medicines which are sold at the nearest chicken feed places.

Tabel 1. Performance of Laying Hens

Performance	Laying Chickens		
	2020	2021	2022
Production period (Weeks)	17 - 50	17 - 60	17 - 60
Body weight (Kg)	1,7	1,8	1,8
Egg production per day	50	40	335
Egg weight (g)	47	47	52
Number of eggs per week	350	280	2.345
Daily feeding (Kg)	4,95	3,96	33

LITERATURE REVIEW

A business or business feasibility study is a way of determining whether a business is worth running or not. With this business or business feasibility study, we will be able to assess the condition of the business and what benefits can be generated from the business that will be run.

According to Dr. Muhammad Busro (2017:3) As explained above, there are many goals to be achieved when conducting a business feasibility study.

- a. The business undertaken can be successful, in the sense that the capital can be returned within a certain time, and the capital can even grow.
- b. the rest of the business as income while increasing capital.
- c. not closing in the middle of the road, in the sense that the business being carried out can survive, not stopping before the capital is returned, whether this is because it is not selling, there are no buyers or requests for services, it is unable to compete with similar businesses, both those around the place of business and in other areas .
- d. not be less competitive with other people's businesses in the sense that the business carried out has the ability to match or even be able to beat other business competitors.
- e. can develop sustainably in the sense of not just standing in place, or running in place, but even though slowly, but can definitely move forward according to the targets that have been set.
- f. can be used as a source of income in the sense that we as business people receive a salary or income commensurate with our hard work.
- g. can be used as a source of increased capital, in the sense that the capital invested is not only nominally fixed but can grow.

When setting up a business, what must be paid attention to is fulfilling the provisions on aspects such as marketing aspects, financial aspects and environmental aspects of livestock, regarding legal aspects in terms of processing legal and illegal documents, it is still not mandatory, because it is still a small-scale farm.

Marketing Aspect

According to Philip Kotler (2013:1) Marketing is a human activity directed at business to satisfy wants and needs through an exchange process. Examples of marketing aspects:

1. Egg production is the number of eggs produced by each individual chicken during the laying period (Baktiningsih et al., 2013);
2. Price According to Ramli (2013), the definition of price is the relative value of a product;
3. Distribution According to Subagyo, Nur, & Indra (2018) Distribution is the movement or transfer of goods or services from the source to the final consumer, consumer or user, through distribution channels, and payment movements in the opposite direction, up to original manufacturer or supplier;
4. Promotion According to Laksana (2019: 129) "promotion is a communication between sellers and buyers that comes from the right information which aims to change the attitudes and behavior of buyers, who previously did not know them, become familiar so they become buyers and still remember the product. The marketing aspect is used to find out what is needed in the market and becomes a benchmark in marketing the egg products that you want to allocate to whether there are more or less fans. Like traditional local grocery markets, there is a lot of demand for eggs per day, estimated at up to 40 kg, and at grocery stalls, the daily demand for eggs is only up to 20 kg.

Financial Aspect

The financial aspect is used as the main capital in running the initial laying chicken business from seedlings to adults, fixed costs, variable costs and also becomes transaction data on sales, whether profit or loss.

In the financial aspect, there is a formula for determining income data, namely:

1. Total costs or Total Cost (TC)
namely all costs incurred in the livestock production process. With the formulation:

$$TC = TFV + TVC$$

Where:

TC (total Cost) = Total Cost

TFV (Total Fixed Cost)= Fixed Cost

TVC (Total Variable cost)=Variable Cost

2. Acceptance
According to Erliana (2017:17) revenue is the value of money obtained from production results or the results received by farmers from selling production output. The formula for acceptance is:

$$TR = Pq \times Q$$

Where:

TR: Total Sales

Q: Selling price

Q: Total Production Profit

3. Profits

Profits the difference between total revenue and total costs incurred by the farmer, where the profit formula is:

$$K=TR-TC$$

Where:

K: Profit

TR: Total Sales

TC: Total Production Cost

Environmental Aspects of Livestock

Environmental aspects of livestock are defined as elements of laying hen cage activities that can interact with the environment. Examples: Consuming clean water, filtering cage air filters, providing disinfectant to cages, etc. In this case, the environmental aspect of livestock also means maintaining cleanliness in the cage, maintaining the quality of the feed and caring for the cage and laying hens so that the quality of the eggs produced will be better and the resulting production will increase.

According to Sihombing (The livestock environment is all the physical, chemical, biological and social factors that exist around livestock. These factors include climate (temperature, light, humidity), livestock behavior, causes of disease, and livestock management (enclosures). , feeding and drinking, maintenance).

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In this chart the author will explain the framework for thinking about business feasibility for laying hen breeders through interviews with 3 informants and carrying out direct observations or observations by looking at marketing aspects, financial aspects and environmental aspects.

Figure 1. Business Feasibility Framework

METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is a combined type, namely qualitative and quantitative methods. In the marketing and environmental aspects, qualitative methods are used, while in the financial aspects, quantitative methods are used. Data yang digunakan adalah data primer dan skunder. Informan Penelitian ada 3 orang, pemilik dan 2 orang karyawan.

Collecting observational data or direct observations from livestock is looked at in 3 aspects, namely finance, marketing and the environment. After obtaining the direct data, the author provides the results in the observation results column to describe the situation in the field which the author has directly reviewed and provides a decision as to whether or not the business is feasible from the results of direct observations regarding financial, marketing and environmental aspects.

In the data analysis method, the author collects the results of answers from all informants and observations from the location to be filtered into accurate data

so that it can be used to make decisions on the results of business feasibility analysis, following 3 data analyzes:

1. Data Reduction

Data reduction is a process of summarizing or selecting the main things. Because the amount of data obtained from the field is quite large, it needs to be recorded carefully and in detail.

2. Data Presentation

After the data reduction process, the step the researcher took was to present the data. We can present data in two forms of presentation, namely tables and diagrams.

3. Drawing Conclusions

The final step in data collection is drawing conclusions and verification. The process starts from the beginning of data collection, then the researcher summarizes the problems in the field, then takes notes until drawing conclusions. Usually initial conclusions are still temporary and may change while the data collection process is still ongoing. However, this conclusion can be a credible conclusion if it is supported by valid and consistent data (Rijali, 2018).

RESULT

This research has explained 3 data aspects that will determine its feasibility, namely marketing aspects, financial aspects and environmental aspects of livestock. Researchers first discuss findings regarding marketing aspects that will determine the feasibility of the laying chicken business. This research found 3 points in the marketing aspect of laying hen farming, namely the production of eggs obtained, the selling price of eggs and the distribution of eggs.

The first finding was the egg production obtained. In 2020 egg production will be around 50 eggs per day or 18,250 eggs per year from 50 laying hens. In 2021 egg production will be around 40 eggs per day or 14,600 eggs per year from 40 laying hens. In 2022 egg production will be around 335 eggs per day or 122,275 eggs per year from 335 laying hens. Egg production is the number of eggs produced by each individual chicken during the laying period (Baktiningsih et al., 2013). This is in line with the research results of Nurjannah, Sitti Hajerah Hasyim and Anisa Nurulita Hasani. Vol. 5 No.4 2022 that Based on statistical data from South Sulawesi Province regarding egg production from laying hens from 2016-2020, there was an increase in 2017 amounting to 147,554.75 tonnes from 2016 which was 90,513.88 tonnes then in 2018 egg production experienced a slight decrease to 140,662.17 tons. Then in 2019, egg production increased rapidly to reach 194,650.44 tons. This increase in egg production continued to increase in 2020, reaching 206,598.22 tons. The following is a graph regarding the egg production of laying hens in South Sulawesi province.

The second point of finding from the marketing aspect is the selling price of eggs. Due to the fluctuating price of eggs each month, 20,000 - 29,000 per kilogram, in 2020, 2021 and 2022 they will be sold per kilo at an average price of IDR 25,000 minus 500 rupiah in 2022 to ensure customers do not buy from agents. According to Ramli (2013), price is the relative value of a product. This is almost

in line with the pricing method used in sales from the research results of Nurjannah, Sitti Hajerah Hasyim and Anisa Nurulita Hasani. Vol. 5 No.4 2022 that in overcoming egg price competition on the market, Mr. Tahar overcomes it by determining prices. This price determination is carried out through coordination within the egg farmer group so that an agreement is reached in determining the price and preventing competition between egg farmers

The third point of finding from the marketing aspect is the price of egg distribution. In 2020, it will be distributed to just 1 stall every week, weighing 20 kg. In 2021, it will be distributed to just 1 stall every week, weighing 16 kg. In 2022, distribution to stalls will increase with demand for around 15-19 kilograms every day with a weight of 19.7 kg. According to Subagyo, Nur, & Indra (2018) Distribution is the movement or movement of goods or services from the source to the final consumer, consumer or user, through distribution channels, and payment movements in the opposite direction, up to the original producer or supplier. This is not in line because the results of the researchers' findings were on a small scale so they only directly delivered the eggs to the nearest shop and entrusted them to neighbors, whereas from the research results of Nurjannah, Sitti Hajerah Hasyim and Anisa Nurulita Hasani. Vol. 5 No.4 2022 The marketing strategy he uses is to offer or contact egg distributors to be able to sell egg products to the market.

Furthermore, this research has discovered the financial aspect. This research has data on business income in the financial aspect for 3 years, namely 2020, 2021 and 2022 which is calculated using a quantitative method using the calculation formula: $K=TR-TC$, where: K: Profit, TR: Total Sales, TC: Total Production Costs.

Business income data on financial aspects 2020. Total sales obtained were Rp. 26,825,000. The total costs incurred were Rp. 18,944,700. Calculation: $K=26,825,000 - 18,944,700$. $K= 7,880,300$. So the profit earned for 1 year in 2020 is 7,880,300 from a total of 50 laying hens.

Business income data on financial aspects 2021. Total sales obtained were Rp. 21,475,000. The total costs incurred were Rp. 12,265,200. Calculation: $K=21,475,000 - 12,265,200$. $K= 9,209,800$. So the profit earned for 1 year in 2021 is 9,209,800 from a total of 40 laying hens.

Business income data on financial aspects 2022. Total sales obtained were Rp. 179,800,000 and the total costs incurred were Rp. 110,794,800. Calculation: $K=179,800,000 - 110,794,800$. $K= 69,005,200$. So the profit earned for 1 year in 2022 is 69,005,200 from a total of 335 laying hens.

According to Erwin and Sri Handini (2020:2) Financial Management is the management of financial functions, namely how to obtain funds and how to use funds. The researchers used this formula from the research results of Nuraviva Salehani, Tharsisius Pabendon. Vol 6 No 2 (2022). That in the financial aspect there is a formula for determining income data, namely: $K=TR-TC$ Where: K: Profit, TR: Total Sales and TC: Total Production Costs.

Lastly, this research has discovered environmental aspects of livestock. In the aspect of the livestock environment, there are data findings for 3 years, namely 2020-2022, with the development of the livestock environment which is equipped with the help of laying hen farming equipment.

Livestock environmental data in 2020-2021 is because there are around 40-50 chickens, so you only need to clean the droppings every 1-2 weeks, the droppings are thrown away in a special room and the droppings are diluted and then drained into the sewer. As for the air above the house, it is an open space so the air goes straight in and out or you could say natural air and also provides medicines to maintain the health of the chickens so that the environment is not infected with diseases that cause disease attacks in other chickens and in 2022 in terms of The livestock environment here we use is 4 meters wide or on a small scale in the houses that we make as far as possible from various diseases, the air uses exhaust air so that the room air is not hot and stuffy or even dirty air, we try to do this by spraying disinfectant in the cage room every cleaning the chicken droppings, don't forget to give the nd ib vaccine about once every 3 months and nd ai only once. As for medicines for chicken health, we provide and provide tools as well as pills and powders such as exitor worms to cure worms in chickens, tetrachlor for health care complete in 1 package in pill form and trimezin for treatment in powder or powder form, then for the chicken manure we clean it once every day and throw it in an empty land disposal site and water with the manure diluted. According to Sihombing (The livestock environment is all the physical, chemical, biological and social factors that exist around livestock. These factors include climate (temperature, light, humidity), livestock behavior, causes of disease, and livestock management (pen , feeding and drinking, maintenance). This compares innovatively with research from Nuraviva Salehani, Tharsisius Pabendon. Vol 6 No 2 (2022). Analysis of the feasibility of the Independent Laying Chicken Farming business. Environmental aspects of Independent Farming pay great attention to the cleanliness of the cages by routinely sowing sawdust onto the floor of the cage so that there are no flies or other insects, it also does not pollute the air with unpleasant odors, and the waste produced from the farm is not thrown away but is processed into fertilizer. Independent livestock farming also has a positive impact on the surrounding land ecosystem using chicken manure. can be used as fertilizer and make the land fertile and also independent livestock farming is well received by the surrounding community because it does not interfere with people's daily activities. Environmental aspects are able to provide benefits and have a good impact on the surrounding environment and do not harm the people who live around the farm.

DISCUSSION

Marketing Aspect, In the marketing aspect, for 3 years, sales are still at the stage of selling them to the nearest stalls which do not incur shipping costs in order to get subscriptions for selling the eggs, while the rest they entrust to relatives and neighbors, some even sell directly per kilogram. set at the agent's price without deducting 500 rupiah, while for large wholesale purchases it will be reduced by 500 rupiah.

Financial Aspect, In the financial aspect of laying hens that has been described, it is considered profitable and there are very minimal losses, even at the beginning of the first year they have very little maintenance but they can still turn over their capital in the business of selling these eggs, from this it can be concluded that the turnover increases every year. obtained increases over time, such as in 2020 with a net income of Rp. 7,880,300. then in 2021 with net income of IDR. 6,086,840. and finally in 2022 with net income of IDR. 68,205,200. It's really fast, isn't it, therefore for this financial aspect, God willing, it can be concluded that it is worth running.

Livestock Environmental Aspects: In the livestock environmental aspects that have been explained, there is a lot of explanation in terms of cleaning cages, preventing disease in livestock chickens in order to reduce the occurrence of an unhealthy livestock environment and also reduce the death rate in these livestock animals. There are two explanations for the condition of the livestock environment, namely cleaning the cages and maintaining the health of livestock. Based on the results of field observations, modern tools are not yet sufficient to maintain the cleanliness of the livestock environment, it still uses human labor but with daily cleanliness you can still get a healthy livestock environment. and good. So from this explanation it can be concluded that the environmental aspect of livestock is adequate in terms of health and cleanliness in both the cage and the livestock.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In the marketing aspect, we still use traditional marketing with small scale sales by entrusting them to nearby stalls. In the financial aspect, it can be said to be profitable and there are very few losses. Meanwhile, regarding the environmental aspect, there are no modern tools for cleaning chicken coops and their environment. It can be recommended that the marketing of egg sales is worthy of continuing because it helps the economy of the stalls and nearby households.

FURTHER STUDY

The author's suggestion is that at the livestock environment stage, automatic cleaning equipment should be further developed.

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